

Appendix

This document contains an extensive analysis of Sentiment Analysis (Table 1) and Topic Modelling (Table 2) methods, tools and accuracy results from the reviewed research works in the context of the paper entitled “*Data Analytics methods to measure Service Quality: A systematic review*”.

Table 1 - Sentiment Analysis in reviewed works

Reference	Method	Techniques	Tool	Accuracy
(Lee, et al., 2021)	Mixed	Lexicon-based and ML approach to check accuracy	AFINN, New Lexicon (NHSdict), Integrated dictionary, Logistic, Lasso, Ridge and elastic regression	69% classified as expressing the same sentiment by both dictionaries
(Svartzman, et al., 2020)	ML approach	ML approach with VADER	VADER, Colneriç and Demsar’s (2018) model for emotion recognition	In the past three years Gilbert’s (2014) VADER sentiment analysis has proven to outperform other methods for sentiment analysis in social media.
(Martin-Domingo, et al., 2019)	Mixed	Commercial tools and ML approach to check accuracy	Twinword, Theysay, Manual classification	Theysay outperforms Twinword in the percentage of tweets correctly analysed (78.7% vs. 69.6%)
(Barakat, et al., 2021)	ML approach	ML approach - CNN and LSTM	Pretrained word embedding for English by Stanford University, Authors trained own word embedding for Arabic	LSTM is slightly better than CNN (0.817 accuracy and 0.814 F1-score in LHR dataset)
(Kar, 2020)	ML approach	ML approach - For each topic, a 5-point sentiment score was computed and then mapped with	Stanford CoreNLP toolkit for scoring of sentiments in terms of polarity	-

		the outputs of the content analysis of the topic models		
(Gitto & Mancuso, 2017)	Commercial tool	Commercial Tool	Semantria	-
(Lee & Yu, 2018)	Lexicon-Based	Lexicon-Based	AFINN, NRC Emotion and Bing Liu lexicons, customized lexicon ; R programming language	AFINN showed the best pre-test performance in our dataset; Spearman's correlations between Google reviews and ASQ ratings improve over time as the number of reviews increase
(Shah, et al., 2020)	ML approach	ML approach - Classification of three input variables including text reviews, images, and a combination of text and visual contents – Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, logistic regression, Lazy.IBK, J.48, SVM, and CNN–LSTM	Python Stanford CoreNLP	LSTM models outperformed baseline models by 10% in terms of accuracy on textual dataset (0.95 accuracy).Fusing the textual and visual dataset, the model accuracy has improved by 12.64%
(Chinsha & Shibily, 2014)	Lexicon-Based	Lexicon-Based	SentiWordNet lexicon	-
(Shah, et al., 2021)	ML approach	ML approach using SVM, ELM and Lexicon-Based approach	SenticNet lexicon	The proposed approach outperformed other existing methods (i.e., accuracy 91.5% and precision 89.2%).
(Zhao, et al., 2019)	ML approach	ML approach using Naïve Bayes	TextBlob, Stanford Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK)	Polarity and subjectivity calculation

(Liu, et al., 2019)	ML approach	ML approach using Naïve Bayes	SnowNLP	Manual classification and comparison of accuracy (SnowNLP accuracy rate 71.1% based on comparison to the result of user ratings, and user ratings accuracy rate based on the comparison to manual calibration was 85%)
(Rus, et al., 2019)	ML approach	ML approach using VADER	VADER, Python3.6	Sentiment is calculated automatically for each HOLSERV Plus dimension
(Gupta, et al., 2018)	ML approach	ML approach using C4.5 Decision Tree	-	Using confusion matrix, the accuracy of the rule is 93,75%
(Chakrabarti, et al., 2018)	Lexicon-Based	Lexicon-Based	AFINN, Bing, NRC lexicons; R package	-
(Putri & Alamsyah, 2017)	ML approach	ML approach using Naïve Bayes	RapidMiner 7.3	92% precision, 89.67% recall, 90% accuracy, and 0.874 kappa
(Prameswari, et al., 2017)	ML approach	ML approach using RNTN	Sentiment Treebank	average accuracy of 85%, while average value of F1 Measure is 77%. The positive category has the highest value of F1 Measure (90%.)
(Ceyhan, et al., 2017)	ML approach	ML approach using Naïve Bayes, SMO, J48	WEKA	The best ML algorithm for each of the methods is the NB ranging from 85% to 98% accuracy, while the poorest results are taken from J48 ranging from 85% to 89% accuracy.
(Chiu, et al., 2015)	Mixed	ML approach combined with	HowNet and NTUSD lexicons; WEKA	The values of precision, recall, and

		Lexicon-Based (for words that cannot be retrieved from lexicons, ML approach is used: supervised SO_PMI, Unsupervised SO_PMI, Supervised SO_TF, Unsupervised SO_TF)		F-measure of supervised SO_PMI range between 84.21% and 91.20%
(Jung, et al., 2015)	ML approach	ML approach using classification	-	78% average precision
(Duan, et al., 2013)	ML approach	ML approach using Naïve Bayes	NLTK	-
(Zvarevashe & Olugbara, 2018)	ML approach	ML approach using Naive Bayes multinomial (NBM), Sequential minimal optimization (SMO), Compliment Naive Bayes (CNB) and Composite hypercubes on iterated random projections (CHIRP)	Python, TextBlob	Naïve Bayes multinomial algorithm had the highest precision which reached 80.9%
(Fachrina & Widyantoro, 2017)	ML approach	ML approach using SVM & Naïve Bayes Classifiers and Rule-based approach for sentiment classification	WEKA	Support Vector Machine shows better performance and for most aspects have highest F-measure compared to NB or rule-based.

(Tilahun & Sharma, 2015)	Lexicon-Based	Lexicon-Based	-	Polarity determination: 100% precision, average recall 90.85%
(He, et al., 2018)	Commercial tool	Commercial tool	Lexalytics	-
(Tian, et al., 2019)	Lexicon-Based	Lexicon-Based	ANEW and custom	-

Table 2 - Topic Modelling in reviewed works

Reference	Techniques	Tool	Accuracy
(Lee, et al., 2021)	LDA, Support vector machine, Naïve Bayes, Decision tree, K-nearest neighbors, Neural networks, Random Forest	R, Python	Classification of dimensions from LDA into SERVQUAL
(Svartzman, et al., 2020)	k-means ++	-	Elbow method to identify optimal number of topics
(Martin-Domingo, et al., 2019)	Keyword Classification - Segmentation done with individual keywords, mapping all to a hierarchical list of processes and attributes.	Manually, definition of list of processes and attributes	Sentiment analysis used to measure ASQ for each attribute and process
(Barakat, et al., 2021)	Keyword Classification - Segmentation done with individual keywords, mapping all to a hierarchical list of processes and attributes	Manually, definition of list of 23 attributes under 9 categories	Models trained with aviation related data performed better than those trained with general purpose data when measuring ASQ per attribute
(Kar, 2020)	LDA	-	A network diagram enables the visualization between topics which co-occur together based on text summarization
(Shadiyar, et al., 2020)	Keyword Classification	CONCOR analysis using UCINET	Comparison between CIS and

			Korean airlines' clusters from CONCOR analysis
(Gitto & Mancuso, 2017)	Keyword Classification	Classification to Aviation and Non-aviation services	Evaluations for the aviation services mostly concern check-in, baggage claim and security control procedures.
(Ban & Kim, 2019)	Semantic Network Analysis - Keywords frequency and centrality analysis	CONCOR analysis using UCINET	-
(Lee & Yu, 2018)	LDA	R package <i>ldatuning</i>	Comparison of 25 derived topics and their frequency with ASQ
(Korfiatis, et al., 2019)	Structural Topic Models	Using FREX criterion, a 20-topic solution had the best relationship between heldout likelihood, semantic coherence, and exclusivity.	To evaluate quality dimensions
(Palese & Usai, 2018)	Weakly supervised topic model	<i>topicmodels</i> package in R programming language	To extract the dimensions of service quality from reviews using SERVQUAL dimensions as aspects. Validation using independent raters - 93.3% accuracy
(Nilashi, et al., 2019)	LDA	-	To discover the main dimensions of satisfaction from the text-based reviews
(Chinsha & Shibily, 2014)	Aspect classification	Stanford PoS tagger	-
(Annisa, et al., 2019)	LDA	-	The best coherence score comes from 8

			number of topics extracted.
(Hou, et al., 2019)	Semantic Association Network	Gephi, ForceAtlas2	-
(Liu, et al., 2019)	Co-occurrence analysis	Fruchterman-Reingold algorithm to build a layout that well reflects the characteristics and commonness of the different classes of high-frequency word	-
(Rus, et al., 2019)	SVM, Naïve Bayes, k-Nearest Neighbor	Python3.6	Support Vector Machine produces the same value for its accuracy, precision and F1 score, which is 81%, while Naïve Bayes and k-Nearest Neighbor produce values that are not much different, which is around 76%
(Chakrabarti, et al., 2018)	RATER dimensions assignment based on Keyword Extraction	-	-
(Prameswari, et al., 2017)	Aspect classification	PoS Tagging, Taxonomy Formulation	-
(Guo, et al., 2017)	LDA	Stanford Topic Modelling Toolbox version 0.4.0	The Jaccard coefficient is 0.66 and 0.76 between the automated analysis and two researchers.
(Jung, et al., 2015)	Dictionary-based named entity recognition from high frequency terms	-	0.95 precision, 0.91 F1-score, 0.87 recall
(Duan, et al., 2013)	Keyword extraction to represent the five SERVPERF dimensions		the proposed five-dimension classification algorithm get 0.68 F-measure and positive-negative sentiment

			classification algorithm get 0.91 F-measure on the test set.
(Thuy, et al., 2018)	Aspect extraction and classification using ML (SVM)	-	For the WEmb model 72.33% in the F1 score
(Fachrina & Widyanoro, 2017)	SVM & Naïve Bayes Classifiers	WEKA	-
(Tilahun & Sharma, 2015)	Keyword Lexicon	-	classification of specific categories: precision 87.3% and recall 85.8%.
(He, et al., 2018)	Keyword Classification - Segmentation with individual keywords, mapping to 7 SERVQUAL dimensions	Manually, definition of list of keywords per dimension	Sentiment analysis used to measure service quality for each dimension

Bibliography

- Annisa, R., Surjandari, I. & Zulkarnain, Z., 2019. Opinion Mining on Mandalika Hotel Reviews Using Latent Dirichlet Allocation. *Procedia Computer Science*, Volume 161, pp. 739-746.
- Ban, H.-J. & Kim, H.-S., 2019. Understanding Customer Experience and Satisfaction through Airline Passengers' Online Review. *Sustainability*, 11(5), p. 4066.
- Barakat, H., Yeniterzi, R. & Martín-Domingo, L., 2021. Applying deep learning models to twitter data to detect airport service quality,. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, Volume 91, p. 102003.
- Ceyhan, M., Orhan, Z. & Domnori, E., 2017. *Health service quality measurement from patient reviews in Turkish by opinion mining*. Singapore, Springer Nature , pp. 649-653.
- Chakrabarti, S., Trehan, D. & Makhija, M., 2018. Assessment of service quality using text mining – evidence from private sector banks in India. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*.
- Chinsha, T. C. & Shibily, J., 2014. Aspect based Opinion Mining from Restaurant Reviews. *International Journal of Computer Applications*.
- Chiu, C., Chiu, N.-H., Sung, R.-J. & Hsieh, P.-Y., 2015. Opinion mining of hotel customer-generated contents in Chinese weblogs. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 18(5), pp. 477-495.
- Duan, W., Cao, Q., Yu, Y. & Levy, S., 2013 . *Mining Online User-Generated Content: Using Sentiment Analysis Technique to Study Hotel Service Quality*., s.l., IEEE, pp. 3119-3128.
- Fachrina, Z. & Widyanoro, D. H., 2017. *Aspect-Sentiment Classification in Opinion Mining using the Combination of Rule-Based and Machine Learning*. s.l., s.n.
- Gitto, S. & Mancuso, P., 2017. Improving airport services using sentiment analysis of the websites. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, Volume 22, pp. 132-136.

- Guo, Y., Barnes, S. & Jia, Q., 2017 . Mining meaning from online ratings and reviews: Tourist satisfaction analysis using latent dirichlet allocation. *Tourism Management*, pp. 467-483.
- Gupta, S., Jain, S. & Gupta, S., 2018. OPINION MINING FOR HOTEL RATING THROUGH REVIEWS USING DECISION TREE CLASSIFICATION METHOD. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science*, 9(2).
- He, W. et al., 2018. Measuring and comparing service quality metrics through social media analytics: a case study. *Information Systems and e-Business Management*, p. 579–600.
- Hou, Z. et al., 2019. Opinion mining from online travel reviews: A comparative analysis of Chinese major OTAs using semantic association analysis. *Tourism Management*, pp. 276-289.
- Jung, Y., Hur, C., Jung, D. & Kim, M., 2015. Identifying key hospital service quality factors in online health communities. *J Med Internet Res.*, 17(4).
- Kar, A., 2020. What Affects Usage Satisfaction in Mobile Payments? Modelling User Generated Content to Develop the “Digital Service Usage Satisfaction Model”. *Inf Syst Front* .
- Korfiatis, N., Stamolampros, P., Kourouthanassis, P. & Sagiadinos, V., 2019. Measuring service quality from unstructured data: A topic modeling application on airline passengers’ online reviews. *Expert Systems with Applications*, Volume 116, pp. 472-486.
- Lee, H. J., Lee, M., Lee, H. & Cruz, R. A., 2021. Mining service quality feedback from social media: A computational analytics method. *Government Information Quarterly*, 38(2), p. 101571.
- Lee, K. & Yu, C., 2018. Assessment of airport service quality: A complementary approach to measure perceived service quality based on Google reviews. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, Volume 71, pp. 28-44.
- Liu, Y., Li, Y. & Li, W., 2019. Natural language processing approach for appraisal of passenger satisfaction and service quality of public transportation. *IET Intelligent Transport Systems*, 13(11), pp. 1701-1707.
- Martin-Domingo, L., Martín, J. C. & Mandsberg, G., 2019. Social media as a resource for sentiment analysis of Airport Service Quality (ASQ). *Journal of Air Transport Management*, Volume 78, pp. 106-115.
- Nilashi, M. et al., 2019. A Hybrid Method with TOPSIS and Machine Learning Techniques for Sustainable Development of Green Hotels Considering Online Reviews. *Sustainability*, 11(21), p. 6013.
- Palese, B. & Usai, A., 2018. The relative importance of service quality dimensions in E-commerce experiences. *International Journal of Information Management*, Volume 40, pp. 132-140.
- Prameswari, P., Surjandari, I. & Laoh, E., 2017. *Opinion Mining from Online Reviews in Bali Tourist Area*. s.l., IEEE.
- Putri, N. A. S. & Alamsyah, A., 2017. OPINION MINING OF TRIPADVISOR REVIEW TOWARDS FIVE-STAR HOTELS IN BANDUNG CITY. *e-Proceeding of Management* , p. 572.
- Rus, A. M. M., Annisa, R., Surjandari, I. & Zulkarnain, 2019. Measuring Hotel Service Quality in Borobudur Temple Using Opinion Mining. *2019 16th International Conference on Service Systems and Service Management (ICSSSM)*, pp. 1-5.
- Shadiyar, A., Ban, H.-J. & Kim, H.-S., 2020. Extracting Key Drivers of Air Passenger’s Experience and Satisfaction through Online Review Analysis. *Sustainability*, 12(21), p. 9188.

- Shah, A. M., Yan, X., Shah, S. A. A. & Mamirkulova, G., 2020. Mining patient opinion to evaluate the service quality in healthcare: a deep-learning approach. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing* volume, Volume 11, p. 2925–2942.
- Shah, A., Yan, X., Tariq, S. & Khan, S., 2021. Listening to the patient voice: using a sentic computing model to evaluate physicians' healthcare service quality for strategic planning in hospitals. *Qual Quant* 55, p. 173–201.
- Svartzman, G. G., Ramirez-Marquez, J. E. & Barker, K., 2020. Social media analytics to connect system performability and quality of experience, with an application to Citibike. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, Volume 139.
- Thuy, N. T. T., Bach, N. X. & Phuong, T. M., 2018. *Cross-Language Aspect Extraction for Opinion Mining*. s.l., IEEE.
- Tian, X. et al., 2019. A new approach of social media analytics to predict service quality: evidence from the airline industry. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 33(1).
- Tilahun, T. & Sharma, D. P., 2015. Design and Development of E-Governance Model for Service Quality Enhancement. *Journal of Data Analysis and Information Processing*, 3(3).
- Zhao, Y., Xu, X. & Wang, M., 2019. Predicting overall customer satisfaction: Big data evidence from hotel online textual reviews. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, pp. 111-121.
- Zvarevashe, K. & Olugbara, O. O., 2018. *A Framework for Sentiment Analysis with Opinion Mining of Hotel Reviews*. s.l., IEEE.